

KEY CONCEPTS THAT EXPLAIN THE ESSENCE OF THE TERM “READING CULTURE”

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***Abstract.** One of the most significant achievements of individuals and society throughout human history is the possession and reading of books. Through books, it becomes possible to overcome the barriers between chronological eras and familiarize oneself with the knowledge accumulated by humanity, as well as with the ideas, educational concepts, and theories developed over the course of historical and social progress. The attitude toward books and reading contributes to a person’s moral, intellectual, and aesthetic development, self-improvement, and enrichment of worldview. For this reason, humanity’s relationship with books has maintained a positive character over the centuries. The education of younger generations has also focused on fostering a positive attitude toward books in them. An individual’s positive relationship with books and reading finds its expression in the concept of “reading culture.” The article explores the key concepts that illuminate the essence of the term “reading culture.”*

***Keywords:** book, printed book, electronic book, reader, reading, reading culture.*

Introduction

One of the miracles created by mankind in the course of its historical development is a book. With the help of books, knowledge is acquired and conclusions are made about the entire history of mankind, the socio-cultural way of life of individual peoples, nations and ethnic groups, the role of various cultural phenomena in social dialectics, their influence on human civilization, the achievements and mistakes of society in science, technology, engineering, as well as in all spheres of public life. At the same time, new knowledge is formed on the basis of books and the ideas put forward in them.

That is to say, the underlying principle here is that the most important socio-pedagogical value of books is determined by their ability to acquire knowledge, develop thinking, perception and reasoning, expand the worldview, "form a positive character, teach ways of resolving life and life's contradictions" [11, - p. 38], study foreign languages, "enrich the vocabulary" in the language being studied [10, - p. 921]. The economy of books is determined by the relatively low cost of their acquisition and use, their availability in information resource centers of state and educational institutions, as well as through special free sites (for example, Ziyonet).

Before discussing student reading, it is necessary to understand the definition of the concepts of "reading", "reading books", "book reading culture".

To be more precise, it can be stated that sources explain the concept of "reading" as follows: a type of speech activity aimed at perceiving a graphically recorded text by its content [16]; a specific form of speech activity manifested in the correspondence of the essence of the text to the communicative requirements of the content of the graphic record during reception and processing [10, - p. 920]; a speech process that, like any mental and cognitive activity of a person, ensures the implementation of new higher reflex functions [6].

Indeed, in the process of reading, which has a speech character, mental and cognitive activity is manifested, and in essence, on the basis of the graphic form of the text, the assimilation, perception of its content and processing of the assimilated information occurs.

According to A.A. Umarov, cognition that occurs in the process of activity, the acquisition of knowledge is a phenomenon characteristic of the acquisition of knowledge, which is based on activity, purposeful reading and assimilation of information in the text in accordance with the various needs of the social subject [14, p. 88]. The author's approach is ambiguous. In our opinion, the following statement would give a clearer expression of the author's thoughts: reading is a process of activity aimed at cognition, understanding and education, a social and individual phenomenon inherent in a person or social subjects, which is based on attitude, activity, purposefulness (or direction), the need for reading, as well as the need to assimilate information and data contained in the relevant text.

In the sources, along with the concept of "reading", the term "reading culture" is also used, and both concepts are different from each other. In our opinion, reading is a person's movement aimed at cognition and understanding, and reading culture is its level, which represents

Results and discussion

The concept of "reading culture" is also interpreted in different ways. For example, reading culture is "knowledge, norms, social phenomena, representing a set of changes occurring in the substantive and structural systems of the process, behavior and activity of social groups, associations and individuals aimed at obtaining general information" [13, p. 74]; the level of development of reading skills and qualifications in a person [12, p. 42]; "the reader's evaluative attitude towards the book being read and its quality" [9].

In our opinion, reading culture is a person's attitude to the text being read, as well as the level of compliance with the rules of correct, fast, expressive and meaningful reading.

The concept of "reading culture" reflects the terms book, book reader, book reading.

The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan provides the following interpretation of the concept of "book": a book is "a means of storing and disseminating information, ideas, images and knowledge, forming socio-political, scientific and aesthetic views; a tool for promoting and educating knowledge; a work of art, scientific work, social literature. According to UNESCO recommendations, a book is conventionally considered to be a non-periodical publication of at least 48 pages, bound in layers" [19, p. 616]. Considering that the source containing this commentary was published a quarter of a century ago, UNESCO's definition of the term "book" is appropriate. Over the past time, under the influence of global informatization, events have occurred that require a logical enrichment of the term "book". Today, there are not only printed publications, but also books presented in electronic form.

An electronic book is "a type of book without paper, without a cover and without glue" [4]. As is clear, this definition could not fully express the essence of an electronic book. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify the concept of "electronic" with the help of devices and equipment, information technologies, which are the main means of creating any product of this type. In short, an electronic book is "a file (text information encoded by certain methods)" [8, - P. 195].

For instance, one might consider the case where the following definitions provide a more complete and detailed description of the general definition of "e-book": an e-book is "a book that is digitized and presented in a book format for reading on various electronic devices (smartphones, tablets, readers), as well as on the device itself, which allows you to get acquainted with sources of this size, and it is supplied in various formats suitable for various programs and gadgets; EPUB,

Fb2, Pdf, RTF, DOC, MOBI, txt are popular formats in which e-books are published" [18]. This type of modern book is also called a non-traditional book, a digital book, an electronic publication.

To illustrate this more concretely, E-books differ from printed books in some characteristics. In them, "two pages are not glued together, since this sharply reduces the font of the letters. The pages are not discrete (separate), but are presented one after another as a "tape", like frames in a movie. In books of this type, images do not combine very well with the text and are perceived as separate "pictures". The concept of "balance" loses its meaning, and the text loses its aesthetic function and becomes only a source of information" [8, - P. 196].

From the ideas expressed, the characteristics of printed and electronic books can be expressed as follows:

1) characteristics typical of printed books: the presence of a cover with a complex design made of hard or soft paper, fabric or leather; multi-layered; the presence of a separate page and an inner (two glued pages) page; the formation of a single book collection (block); stitching, gluing of all pages from the "spine"; pages are attached to the structure from the "spine" using a fabric cover; pages are separated by numbers; The pages are arranged sequentially in accordance with the ordinal numbers; text and images are compatible with each other; the presence of a thin strip or tape indicating the page being read;

2) characteristics typical of a printed book: the absence of a layered and separate, complex cover, presentation in the form of a file; the text is not presented on pages, but in most cases on a "tape", like in films; the text and images are incompatible with each other, the images are presented as separate "pictures".

A bookworm is a book lover, a person who is fond of reading books (adding the suffix -han to the subject creates a positive meaning).

Personal book reading (or book publishing) is the reading activity of a book lover, a person who is fond of reading books; a person's positive attitude towards books, consistent reading.

By way of illustration, it is worth noting that there are also the following approaches to the concept of "reading culture": reading culture - "interest in books, love of reading, familiarity with literature, understanding of books and the rules for working with them, using books in one's activities" [3]; "interest in books and love for them, familiarity with literature, special knowledge of books and working with them, full use of books" (E. Yuldashev) [17, p. 67]; "as a certain place, an integral environment created by the phenomenon of reading for the moral and intellectual harmony of a person" (T.G. Galaktionova) [5, p. 164]; "correct organization of reading taking into account the achievements of technology and hygiene of mental work, using various methods of working with a book that are beneficial regardless of its content, the purpose of reading and time" (A.P. Primakovsky); "a set of knowledge, abilities, skills and qualifications that allow for the effective organization of the reading process, its socially significant focus and the achievement of other goals"; "the stage preceding the access to a printed source and information about it in connection with the motivational environment"; "the period of time that determines the sequence of reading (subsequent understanding of the topic, development of interest in reading, interpersonal communication about what has been read, application of the information received in various spheres of life, etc.), which is directly related to the comprehension (perception, understanding) of the text, its content and the stages occurring during this period" (N.E. Dobrynina) [1]; "a set of knowledge, skills and abilities related to working with a book, the correct organization of the reading process" [15, - P. 146].

From the above definitions it is clear that the concept of "library culture" is interpreted as a social environment, the attitude of a person or society to books, the means of using books, methods and stages, knowledge, skills and abilities of a person to achieve a certain goal. However, in our opinion, none of the above explanations can fully reveal the essence of the concept.

When analyzing the definition given by R.R. Ashrapov to the concept of "library culture" by content, the correctness of our opinion becomes even clearer due to the complexity of the explanation: "complex relations between man and society, conditioned by spiritual needs that contribute to the transformation of man into a personality" [2]. Therefore, firstly, complex relations between man and society are manifested in all forms of social activity; secondly, the conditioning of relations between man and society by needs can be associated with any social, economic and cultural needs and requirements perceived by the individual and social being; thirdly, the phrase "transformation of man into a personality" is logically incorrect, it is not man who becomes a personality, but a personality who becomes a personality; fourthly, the transformation of an individual into a personality occurs not only through reading books, but is associated with social, psychological, pedagogical factors, which are closely related to each other, interconnected.

Thereafter, one must consider the implications of that can also express critical opinions regarding another approach to the author's interpretation of the concept of "reading culture": a person is a person who possesses morality, spirituality, intellect (mental development), creative vitality, and the ability to self-develop.

In our opinion, this definition by R.R. Ashrapov serves to express not his reading culture, but his general culture.

Among the explanations, N.I. Gendina gives a relatively detailed and precise definition of the concept of "library culture". According to the author, book culture is a set of skills for working with books, which includes systematic and continuous reading with a conscious choice of topic, finding the necessary literature with the help of bibliographic indexes, bibliographic and reference equipment, using rational techniques, maximum and deep assimilation of what has been read, as well as a careful attitude to printed literature [7, - P. 5].

The concept of "reading culture" in the given explanation is relatively correct and complete in content, both from the point of view of library work and from the point of view of the individual's attitude to books.

The concept is directly applicable to society and the individual. Accordingly, each of the concepts of "reading culture of society" and "reading culture of the individual" exhibits its own specificity.

Meanwhile, it is also vital to acknowledge that the reading culture of a society is a positive attitude of members of a certain society towards books and reading books, the level of reading (consistent, continuous, constant reading of books).

Based on the opinions of the authors and approaches in the sources, the essence of the main concept can be explained as follows: reading culture is 1) a person's competence, consisting of knowledge, abilities, skills, experience in reading printed and electronic fiction (works) using the service of information and resource centers, bibliographic and reference equipment, Internet technologies of the search engine "Search"; 2) a positive attitude of a person towards books and reading books, the level of reading (consistent, continuous, regular reading of books); 3) the level of a person's ability to correctly, quickly, fluently, expressively read a fiction text (work) and understand its content, perception and interpretation, using reading techniques (slow, regular, fast and selective reading).

Ultimately, these considerations lead to the conclusion that reading culture reflects the following competencies: conscious choice of reading topics; orientation in the system of sources, primarily bibliographic reference books and library catalogues; correct selection of books, sequential, continuous, systematic reading; moving through a book with maximum assimilation and deep understanding of the information read; use and practical application of information obtained from literature; possession of technical means that ensure the generalization of the information read (transcripts, notes, etc.) and their use; careful attitude to printed books and periodicals; compliance with hygienic, physiological and psychological rules for working with books; rational organization of the reading process; choice of tactics and strategy of reading (reading methods, adaptive modification of the reading process and work with publications) [7, - P. 5]; the ability to find and read works of fiction in information resource centers or the "Search" search engine of Internet technologies.

Conclusion

In essence, the findings indicate that the attitude of the individual and society to books and book reading determines the reading culture of the individual and social subjects. Although the problem of the reading culture of an individual and society, its formation and development have been studied in the field of librarianship, literary studies, sociology, psychology and pedagogy within the framework of foreign and domestic studies, a unified opinion on a single interpretation of the basic concept has not been achieved. This creates the need to characterize the concept of "reading culture" based on the ideas put forward in existing scientific studies. This concept is a polysemantic term. Therefore, when clarifying its essence, it is necessary to take into account the integration of the fields of librarianship, literary studies, sociology, psychology and pedagogy. This aspect of the problem was paid attention to during the study.

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